

PROBLEMS OF RESEARCH OF PHRASEOLOGY AND PAREMIAS IN MODERN LINGUISTICS

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Annotation. The article analyzes the axiological component of verbal units that form paremiological funds in languages with different structures. Phrases, proverbs, and sayings reflect national and cultural characteristics and values accepted in a certain ethnic community. The author's understanding of the axiological component is presented, which is interpreted as a value associated with the assessment, present in the semantics of a paremiological unit.

Keywords: phraseology, paremia, lexical semantic meaning, structural and semantic analysis, content analysis, discourse analysis, conceptual approach.

In modern linguistics, the "anthropological turn" has activated new approaches to the study of the phenomena of language and culture. The study of the actual linguistic aspects of functioning, lexical-semantic and pragmatic significance, genesis, morphological and syntactic features of modern phraseology, and paremiology represents a broad field for comprehensive study and analysis by linguists. At this stage, the level of development of modern methodology in the field of humanities opens up broad opportunities for the implementation of multifaceted studies of linguistic material. This inevitably leads the researcher to the need to use a system of methods not only linguistic but also philosophical and cultural ones to describe linguistic units. Modern paremiology is developing as a system of interconnected social and humanitarian paradigms, demonstrating, on the one hand, a variety of approaches and methods for studying paremias, and on the other hand, a common methodological foundation that allows for interdisciplinary research. Modern tasks of studying paremias are set as problem-oriented, i.e. focused not on one specific approach, but on a problem that requires the integration of several areas of knowledge at once. In this vein, for example, studies of proverbs quoted by famous politicians and statesmen have been carried out. Social aspects of the functioning of proverbs have also become the subject of interdisciplinary study. A combination of cognitive and cultural approaches is used to study the picture of the world, and national and ethnic values reflected in proverbs and sayings.

Cognitive linguistics, one of the new and relevant areas of linguistics, has turned its attention to the relationship between language and consciousness because language is a sign system that records the experience of humanity,

which encodes it [3]. Thus, language describes the world through its perception by man. Thus, we can talk about such a concept as a "linguistic picture of the world". The linguistic picture of the world is a set of ideas of the people about reality at a certain stage of people's development, recorded in units of language, an idea of reality reflected in linguistic signs and their meanings - the linguistic division of the world, linguistic ordering.

The linguistic picture of the world in the consciousness of native speakers is a set of concepts and values. This is one of the components of the cognitive level of the linguistic personality, which is very closely connected with culture. Thus, it is impossible not to correlate the concept of the linguistic picture of the world with the slightly narrower concept of "linguoculture", which in turn is culture reflected, reproduced in linguistic signs. The linguistic picture of the world considers linguistic signs as carriers of a special form, making it possible to analyze the language from the point of view of its influence on the consciousness of its speakers and its mediation, it includes both reality and individual features inherent in individual native speakers. By the term "paremia" most modern researchers understand aphorisms of folk origin, primarily proverbs and sayings. Folklore aphorisms, along with aphorisms of non-folklore origin, form a whole layer of linguistic expressions, which is included in the phraseological fund of the language [1]. The question of classifying proverbs and sayings as phraseology remains open since paremias have the characteristics of phraseological units, sentences, and free combinations. In addition, proverbs and sayings are related separately to phraseological units according to different features, and the reason for the difference is the different syntactic nature of these paremias.

In addition to the problem of correlating phraseology and paremiology, separating the concepts of "proverb" and "saying", modern linguistics is also concerned with the issue of distinguishing between paremias and aphorisms. An aphorism is considered a bookish set expression that briefly and originally sets out the author's opinion regarding some life phenomenon or philosophical concept. Paremias are also aphorisms, but they are of folk origin, characterized by laconic form, reproducibility of meaning, and, as a rule, have an edifying meaning. They have an evaluative orientation towards all aspects of human life (from character to activity). Summarizing the concepts distinguished above, we can say the following: phraseological units, paremias, and aphorisms are varieties of set expressions, each of which is characterized by its own set of structural, semantic, and functional features. In a narrow sense, only proverbs

and sayings are considered paremias, since they perform the function of moralizing and can claim the status of exponents of folk wisdom. Paremias are also aphorisms, but they have a folk origin, are characterized by laconic form, reproducibility of meaning, and, as a rule, have an edifying meaning. They have an evaluative orientation towards all aspects of human life (from character to activity). Summarizing the concepts distinguished above, we can say the following: phraseological units, paremias, and aphorisms are types of stable expressions, each of which is characterized by its own set of structural, semantic, and functional features. In a narrow sense, only proverbs and sayings are considered paremias, since they perform the function of moralizing and can claim the status of exponents of folk wisdom. Since paremias are not capable of creating units of speech, they are related to units of language, similar to phraseological units, which gives grounds to attribute them to the phraseological level of language.

I.E. Anichkov considered the issue of idiomaticity of paremias, which is relevant and controversial in 20th-century linguistics. The scientist pointed out the need to study the structural and grammatical component of paremias, suggesting designating proverbs and sayings, which are stable combinations, with the term "idiomatism". [2] However, we note that the issues of classifying paremias as phraseology, as the idiomatic sphere of language, are relevant and not fully resolved for researchers in the field of phraseology and paremiology. Thus, consideration of various interpretations of the concept of paremia allows us to conclude that this linguistic phenomenon has a complex nature and initiates disputes in modern linguistics. The interdisciplinary nature of modern paremiology is largely associated with the development of the communicative-pragmatic paradigm in linguistics, which has shifted the research focus toward speech activity and communication problems. Within the framework of paremiology, this contributed to the study of the functional and pragmatic aspects of proverbs and sayings used in speech, the analysis of the areas of their use, and the associated linguistic, cognitive, social, cultural, and other features of paremias.

Knowledge and active possession of phraseological wealth not only decorate speech but also contribute to a better understanding of the mentality of the people of the studied language. This is all the more important because the problems of communication between cultures and peoples are currently being intensively studied in connection with the increasing importance of knowledge of foreign languages. Proverbs, sayings, and phraseological units are a kind of

exponents of cultural knowledge, where the interaction of linguistic and cultural semantics occurs. That is why the study of phraseological units contributes to the knowledge of the entire history of the development of human society, from the origin of traditions and customs to the achievements of science and technology, and helps to compare the uniqueness of the evolution of two or more separate communities.

Thus, the studies of V.P. Felitsyna, Yu.E. Prokhorov, O.A. Dmitrieva, M.L. Kovshova, F.F. Farkhutdinova, I.V. Privalova, I.V. Siglyuk and other scientists allow us to speak about the special linguacultural status of paremias, since these units most clearly represent the synthesis of linguistic and linguacultural meanings. Summarizing the above, it should be noted that proverbs and sayings most clearly reflect interpersonal relationships, which, being a “mirror” of culture, complexly and repeatedly reflect the self-awareness of the people, their mentality, and vision of the world; this is a product of living speech, the cultural creativity of the people, the purpose of which extends far beyond the framework of an edifying statement. The proverb contains a practical, creative, and philosophical view of the world, which gives it the status of a valuable tool of knowledge.

Conclusion. From all of the above, we can conclude that it is precisely the understanding of the volume and multi-aspect nature of such complex cultural and linguistic phenomena as a riddle and phraseological unit that leads the researcher to the need to apply a comprehensive analysis in his work. In addition, the use of a system of linguistic and cultural-philosophical methods makes it possible to obtain truly comprehensive, objective, and accurate practical results, which, of course, clarifies the thematic classification of riddles and phraseological units, and also sheds light on some aspects of their origin, development, and functioning of the language.

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